

COMPUTER-INTEGRATED DESIGN FOR SHORT FIBRE-REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

The first part of this paper describes an automated system for measuring fibre orientation distribution (FOD) in short fibre-reinforced thermoplastics (SFRTPs). The system involves viewing polished sections through an optical microscope and CCD camera and processing and analysing images using proprietary image analysis software. Detailed measurements of through-thickness fibre orientation distribution are obtained. The second part of the paper describes a computer integrated design procedure which incorporates mould flow analysis, orientation prediction, material property calculations and structural analysis. Computer predicted orientations in flat plaque specimens of 20% GF/PP are compared with experimental values obtained using the automated measurement system. The accuracy of local material property calculations are assessed by testing the plaques in tension and flexure. Good agreement is obtained both for orientation prediction and structural property calculation. The paper concludes that significant progress has been made towards the realisation of a fully integrated design system for SFRTPs.

INTRODUCTION

Short Fibre-Reinforced Thermoplastics (SFRTPs) are an important class of materials being used in an increasing number and variety of applications [1]. However, further expansion of these materials into load bearing and structural applications is being limited by a lack of knowledge on how to design with them. Current methods in design generally use averaged upper and lower bound materials data e.g. stiffness and strength, generally derived from standard test specimens. For complex shapes this data is also used as input to finite element analyses. There are two problems with this approach. Firstly, the materials data obtained from standard tests is often not representative of the material properties in a real component [2]. Secondly, many experimental studies in recent years [3-8] have shown that fibre orientation distribution (FOD) in SFRTPs and hence material properties, depend on the flow conditions in the mould and are a function of both processing parameters and component geometry. For a complex shaped component orientation has also been shown to vary through the wall thickness in a complex way, adding further to the difficulties for the designer. The advancement in computing power, coupled with developments in the theoretical description of fibre orientation and methods of measuring its distribution have resulted in a recent focus of activity aimed at developing

computational methods for the design of SF RTPs [9-12]. The main requirements for computer-integrated design are as follows :-

- (a) Accurate prediction of fibre orientation distribution (FOD) in complex shapes.
- (b) Experimental determination of FOD to validate computer predictions.
- (c) Prediction of local material properties, e.g. stiffness, strength, from FOD.
- (d) Full integration of mould flow analysis, FOD determination, and FE structural analysis.

This paper describes work being done to address the above requirements, the overall aim being to develop a fully integrated design system using computational techniques. The initial focus of the work has been on the measurement and prediction of FOD, however some progress towards structural property determination is also discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF FIBRE ORIENTATION DISTRIBUTION

METHOD

Figure 1. Experimental Determination of Fibre Orientation Distribution

Figure 2. Through-thickness Measure of FOD in a Flat Plaque

An automated system for measuring fibre orientation has been developed (Fig. 1). Cut sections from a component are polished and viewed under a microscope at 50 - 200X magnification. The image is then taken directly into a personal computer (in bit-mapped form) using a CCD camera and frame grabber. The image is processed and analysed using a commercial image processing package, 'Visilog', running on the PC. Particular care has to be taken during the polishing stages to ensure a clear image with minimum fibre damage. The 'Visilog' software is firstly used for image enhancement. This involves thresholding of the grey-scale image and edge detection to identify cut fibre sections and to separate and remove raw inclusions and other debris from the image. The next stage is to analyse all the fibre cross-sections to determine the spacial distribution of fibre orientation. The three dimensional orientation of a fibre can be calculated from measurements of the major and minor axes of the ellipse, formed by the fibre section cutting plane, and its orientation in space [13]. The method adopted uses the 'Visilog' facility for calculating second moments of area of image objects, in this case individual fibre ellipses. Second moment values for all fibres in an image (in addition to fibre position) are output to spreadsheet software which can perform calculation of orientations, determine spacial distribution and plot results as required. The whole process is automated and allows large numbers of images to be processed and analysed rapidly.

RESULTS

To illustrate the complexity of fibre orientation distributions, results from automated measurements on a simple pin-gated flat plaque of dimensions 150mm X 50mm X 4mm (& 2mm) are given. 20% GF Polypropylene is injection moulded into the plaque (in a dual cavity mould) at different injection speeds. Fig. 2 shows the two positions where FOD is measured, 'A' being near the gate and 'B' being halfway along the plaque. Average orientation tensor components (see subsection on orientation prediction) are determined at 13 points through the thickness at each position, each measurement being based on a minimum of 100 fibres. Also shown is an enhanced image through the thickness at position B, clearly illustrating the skin-core effect observed by other authors [3-6].

Fig. 3(a) shows the variation of the tensor components, a_{11} and a_{33} , at position B, for a 4mm plaque at three different fill times, 1, 3 and 10 seconds. a_{11} is a measure of the in-plane orientation in the flow direction and at all speeds has a low value (~ 0.1) in the core region of the plaque rising to a higher value (~ 0.6) in the skin layers. These values are indicative of a transverse alignment in the core and a random-longitudinal alignment in the skin layers, agreeing with previous studies [3,7]. Fig. 3(a) also shows a reduction in a_{11} close to the wall which is thought to be a result of fountain flow and frozen layer effects. Generally, the results show that injection speed appears to have little effect except for some evidence of a greater transverse alignment at high injection speed (1s) at the centre of the core. The a_{33} component is low throughout the thickness, indicating very little out-of-plane alignment, however, at low injection speed (10s) there is a rise in a_{33} at the centre of the plaque section. This is shown in the next paragraph to be related to out-of-plane orientation near the gate.

Fig. 3(b) compares the results at position A with those at position B for the 4 mm plaque at a 1 second fill time. The main difference is that the skin layers near the gate (position A) are more transversely oriented than at the plaque centre (position B), indicated by lower values for a_{11} . The highly divergent flow from the pin gate is the dominant orienting effect in this region, causing transverse alignment, whilst through thickness shear starts to cause more longitudinal orientation in the skin regions as the melt flows down the plaque. a_{33} is generally low near the gate, as it is at position B, however, at the gate there appears to be some evidence of an increase in a_{33} at the centre of the core. This out-of-plane orientation in the core near the gate may be a result of the 3D flow in this region but as fibres move down the plaque, shear forces orient them back into the plane of the plaque. This realignment is less pronounced at slow speeds resulting in residual out-of-plane orientation for the 10 second filling at position B, as observed in the previous paragraph.

Fig. 3(c) compares the results for a 4mm plaque with those for a 2mm plaque at position B for 1 second fill time. Although the maximum and minimum values for a_{11} are similar for both plaques, it is evident that the relative thickness of the core layer, as defined by the positions at which a_{11} starts to fall off, is greater for the 2mm plaque. The boundary between the skin and core layers is controlled by the degree of shear and the viscosity of the melt which is influenced by temperature. For the 2mm plaque, cooling is more rapid resulting in higher viscosity at the same relative position through the thickness. The through thickness shear will therefore result in reduced longitudinal orientation in the 2mm plaque at a corresponding position. Fig. 3(c) also shows that there is minimal out-of-plane alignment in the 2mm plaque at this speed.

These results clearly illustrate the complexity of FOD even in a simple plaque specimen. However, the automated method of measurement provides a valuable tool which will enable computer predictions to be validated.

Figure 3(a). Measured orientation tensor components through the thickness of a 4mm plaque at different injection speeds (Pos. B).

Figure 3(b). Measured orientation tensor components near the gate (Position A) and the centre (Position B) of a 4mm plaque (1s).

Figure 3(c). Measured orientation tensor components at the centre (Position B) of a 4 mm and a 2 mm plaque (1s)

Figure 3(d). Predicted orientation tensor components at the gate (Position A) and centre (Position B) of a 4mm plaque.

INTEGRATED DESIGN PROCEDURE

Figure 4. Overview of the Integrated Design Procedure

Fig. 4 shows an overview of the integrated design procedure under development. Focus of work to date has been on the flow analysis and orientation prediction.

FLOW ANALYSIS AND ORIENTATION PREDICTION

METHOD

Mould filling analysis is conducted using a proprietary computational fluid dynamics package, FLOW3D (CFDS), running on a Sun workstation. A non-isothermal, non-Newtonian transient flow analysis is conducted using finite difference techniques and two-phase flow conditions (polymer and air). The flow front is defined at each time step by the volume fill fraction in each cell. Component geometry is defined using the FLOW3D graphical pre-processor, SOPHIA, which permits complex 3-D shapes to be input and mapped onto a regular multi-block finite difference grid. As through-thickness orientation is important (see earlier section), a minimum of ten layers are defined through the wall of the component. The number of layers chosen depends on the wall thickness and complexity of flow e.g. gate regions may require more. The flow analysis outputs velocities and cell fill fractions at each time step. Details of the component geometry and mesh topology are also stored. The use of a separate flow analysis, in principle, allows this stage of the design procedure to be replaced by an alternative 3rd party mould filling package. The only requirements are that such a package should provide information on flow velocities, mould front progression and mesh geometry throughout the filling process. Through-thickness capability should also be a feature.

The next stage in the design procedure involves the prediction of orientation. The development of suitable methods for describing FOD has made significant strides forward in recent years, mainly as a result of work by Advani, Tucker and others [14-17], who have formulated a concise tensor description which offers considerable advantages for computational prediction. These tensor methods are adopted in this work and for 3D problems involve the determination

of five independent tensor components. A Fortran programme has been written which inputs the component geometry, flow velocities and fill fractions at each time step of the mould filling analysis. The analysis is a general method which is applicable to orientation prediction in 3-D flow. The procedure takes into account both the movement forward of the orientation field with the flow in addition to its change in time under the influence of the velocity field. The programme outputs all components of the orientation tensor at each filled cell for all time steps.

RESULTS

Fig. 3(d) shows the computer predictions for orientation through the thickness of a 4mm 20% GF/PP plaque at positions A and B (see fig. 2). The programme predicts the skin-core structure, with a_{11} being high in the skin layers and low at the centre of the plaque thickness. The low value at the centre is predicted reasonably accurately, however, the value of a_{11} increases to a value significantly higher than that measured at the wall (see fig. 3(a)). The measured reduction at the wall is a consequence of melt cooling and fountain flow effects at the flow front. The latter has not been incorporated in the computer analysis whilst the effect of cooling relies on an accurate model for temperature dependent viscosity. This aspect and the development of the frozen skin layer is currently being investigated. The low values of a_{33} through the complete cross-section, shown in fig. 3(d), agree well with the measured values, confirming the largely inplane flow. The lower values of a_{11} at position A (near the gate), compared to position B, in the skin layers, agrees qualitatively with the measured results. It should be mentioned that actual magnitudes of fibre orientation predictions depend on the assumptions made about the initial orientations at the gate entry. The results shown here are based on initial orientations being average-in-space i.e. $a_{11} = a_{22} = a_{33} = 0.33$, which may differ to actual orientations. There is likely to be some alignment at the gate resulting from the highly divergent flow in this region. Detailed measurements of gate orientations are required to verify this. A further concern about the results in fig. 3(d) is the asymmetry, which, although present in the measured results (see fig. 3(a)), is not evident to the same degree. It appears that the computer predictions are influenced too much, down stream, by the asymmetric position of the gate. This aspect is also being addressed.

STRUCTURAL PROPERTY DETERMINATION AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

Having established the general validity of the computational procedure for determining FOD, current work is focussing on converting the predicted orientations into local material properties which can subsequently be used in finite element analyses. This work is to be reported in detail elsewhere [18], however, an outline of the method and some preliminary results on the prediction of mechanical properties for flat plaque specimens will be given here.

METHOD

The method for determining local material properties is based on the fact that in melt flow situations the fibres tend to align themselves in the plane of flow i.e. parallel to the walls, a fact supported by the low measured values of a_{33} . Only in-plane tensor components, a_{11} , a_{22} and a_{12} are therefore used in the material property calculations. However, orientation does vary through the thickness. For each layer through the thickness, tensor components are combined with the stiffness matrix for fully aligned material of the particular formulation. The latter is calculated using the Halpin-Tsai equations [19]. In effect, each flow layer at a locality is treated as an orthotropic ply within a laminated structure. At each position the local property calculation yields a stiffness matrix for each through-thickness layer. This information is then transferred to a finite element structural analysis package (Pafec-FE). Loading and constraints

are defined and structural calculations conducted using plane stress orthotropic elements in a laminated structure.

RESULTS

To test the above method for predicting local material properties, the measured orientations reported in the earlier section have been used in conjunction with a Halpin-Tsai calculation for aligned 20% GF/Polypropylene. The latter requires data on fibre and resin properties, volume fraction and average fibre length. Calculated values of local tensile modulus (average through-thickness) and flexural modulus at positions 'A' and 'B' in the end-gated plaque have been determined for various conditions. These values are compared with tensile and flexural moduli obtained from test results on 20 mm wide test strips taken from the centre, i.e. across the width, of the injection moulded plaques. These test results give average modulus values over the full length of the plaque, whilst the calculated values are local to positions A and B. The latter are also averaged to give a mean calculated modulus. Table 1 shows the results.

Table 1. Comparison of Predicted Moduli with Measured Moduli for 20% GF/PP

		Predicted Modulus (GPa)		Measured Modulus (Gpa)	
		Tensile	Flexural	Tensile	Flexural
4mm Plaque	Position A	2.659	2.943		
1s fill time	Position B	3.220	3.509		
	Mean	2.940	3.226	3.060	3.597
4mm Plaque	Position A	2.755	3.013		
10s fill time	Position B	3.210	3.449		
	Mean	2.982	3.231	3.050	3.378
2mm Plaque					
3s fill time	Position B	3.078	3.346	2.811	3.724

For the 4 mm plaque (at both 1s and 10s fill times) the mean calculated values for tensile modulus agree well with the test values; 2.2% and 3.9% difference at the two injection speeds. Flexural modulus, however, is underestimated by 4.35% and 10.3% at the two speeds. This underestimate may derive from too much weighting (50%) being given to the position A value which is close to the flexural test supports and thus contributes little to bending deformation. This is supported by the fact that the calculated values at position B are very much closer in value to the test results (< 3% at both speeds).

Comparing position B calculated values for the 2 mm and 4 mm plaques, both tensile and flexural moduli show a reduction, as one would expect from the orientation measurements (see fig. 3(c)). This reduction is only shown in the test results for the tensile modulus. The flexural modulus shows a significant increase in the 2 mm plaque compared to the 4 mm plaque. A possible explanation may lie in the greater contribution to flexural stiffness made by the frozen skin layer where accurate orientation values are difficult to measure in the thinner plaque.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper has reported on some of the foundations which are being laid for the development of a system for integrated design in short fibre-reinforced thermoplastics. The crucial aspect of experimental validation has been addressed by the development of an automated method for measuring orientation using image processing techniques. The results obtained are wholly consistent with reported qualitative studies of through-thickness orientation distribution. There is, however, further need to develop reliable automated methods for better recognition of fibre cross-sections and for minimising the adverse effects of voids, incomplete fibre ellipses and other elements of debris on the quantitative measure of orientation. The tensor approach to describing the orientation state appears to be concise and practical. Its implementation in the proposed design procedure as the basis for predicting orientation distribution is relatively straightforward. However, there are elements of the computer prediction programme which require further development. In particular, the dependence of viscosity on temperature and the formation of orientation in the frozen skin layer needs further study. On the basis of work so far, the laminate model of through-thickness orientation and its use in structural analysis appears to be valid. Reasonable accurate predictions of material properties are achievable. Finally, elements of the design system already in place utilise proprietary software packages requiring significant computing resources. Furthermore, the core calculations involving orientation change and prediction in 3D flow are time consuming. Within the system developed there is scope for improving the efficiency of the computer code, however, it may be some time before a fully integrated design system has been developed for operation on a single workstation or personal computer. The work reported here does, however, show that significant progress towards that goal has been achieved.

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